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FIRST RECORD OF THE GIANT WATER BUG *LETHOCERUS*
(*Hemiptera Heteroptera Belostomatidae*) IN SICILY

SUMMARY

A female specimen of *Lethocerus* cf. *patruelis* (Stål, 1854) was collected near the sea in eastern Sicily. This finding, the first record for the island (and administrative region), is discussed. An updated map at regional scale of *Lethocerus* is provided.

Key words. Catania, first record, Lethocerinae, Nepomorpha.

RIASSUNTO

Prima segnalazione di Lethocerus (Hemiptera Heteroptera Belostomatidae) in Sicilia. Una femmina di *Lethocerus* cfr. *patruelis* (Stål, 1854) è stata raccolta in Sicilia orientale. Si tratta della prima segnalazione per l'isola (e per la corrispondente regione amministrativa). Viene fornita una mappa aggiornata a livello regionale di *Lethocerus*.

Parole chiave. Catania, Lethocerinae, Nepomorpha, prima segnalazione.

INTRODUCTION

The giant water bug genus *Lethocerus* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Belostomatidae) was recorded in Italy less than twenty years ago (see CIANFERONI & NARDI, 2013). In particular, the first published record of *L. patruelis* (Stål, 1854) for this country was provided by BACCHI & RIZZOTTI VLACH (2005) based on a specimen collected in 2000 from Abruzzo, where it was never found again. However, *L. patruelis* was actually detected for the first time in Apulia at least from 1997, confirmed the following year, and found on

several occasions until today (see CIANFERONI & NARDI, 2013, LO PARRINO & TOMASI, 2021 and CIANFERONI & MAZZA 2023 for a summary; LAMANNA & DIMA, 2024). In 2015 this species was recorded from Basilicata by LO PARRINO (2019), in 2018 from northern Calabria and in 2019 from southern Calabria as *L. cf. patruelis* by CASTIGLIONE *et al.* (2021), and in 2023 from Campania as *L. cf. patruelis* by CIANFERONI & MAZZA (2023).

Lethocerus patruelis (Stål, 1854) has an Indo-Mediterranean distribution and it has always been the only species occurring in Europe, reaching the Balkans (cf. PEREZ GOODWYN, 2006; SAREEIN *et al.*, 2009). The relatively recent records from Italy (see e.g., CIANFERONI & NARDI, 2013; LO PARRINO & TOMASI, 2021) and some more northern records from eastern Europe (see e.g., GROZEVA *et al.*, 2013; STOIANOVA & SIMOV, 2016; and CIANFERONI & MAZZA, 2023 for further detail) seem to suggest the tendency of this species to expand. However, the status of this species in Italy is still uncertain since its occurrence can be traced back to both a recent man-mediated unintentional introduction and a natural westward spread (see CIANFERONI & NARDI, 2013; CIANFERONI & MAZZA, 2023).

Moreover, records based on photos or isolated female specimens cannot totally exclude misidentifications with the African closely related species *L. cordofanus* Mayr, 1853 (CIANFERONI & MAZZA, 2023) occurring in the Mediterranean, and recorded in Egypt (PEREZ GOODWYN, 2006) and Israel (NOVOSELSKY *et al.*, 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The discovery of the specimen occurred accidentally. Subsequently, further research (unsuccessful) was carried out by AP to verify the presence of any other specimens. For the material examined the following information is provided: region, municipality (and province), locality, coordinates, date, number of specimens and sex, collector. Geographical coordinates are in decimal degrees (datum WGS84). The uncertainty of data (in metres) was indicated according to the point-radius method (WIECZOREK *et al.*, 2004).

RESULTS

Lethocerus cf. patruelis (Stål, 1854)

Material examined. Sicily: Aci Castello (Catania), Aci Trezza, 37.55998° N 15.15915° E (uncertainty = 4 m), 19.VI.2024, A. Puglisi leg., 1 (Fig. 1), Collection F. Cianferoni (Florence).

Fig. 1 — Female specimen of *Lethocerus* cf. *patruelis* (Stål, 1854) from Aci Trezza (Aci Castello, Catania), Sicily. Body length 78 mm. Photo by F. Cianferoni.

Remarks. A living specimen was observed on 17 June 2014 on the Aci Trezza (Catania) seafront (Fig. 2). After two days (19 June), presumably the same individual was found dead and collected. The second author checked the surroundings, including freshwater sites. However, the research was unsuccessful.

This is the first record for Sicily (Fig. 3). The record is available also from the platform ‘iNaturalist’ (<https://inaturalist.org/>, observation ID 223806355).

Fig. 2 — The site (Aci Trezza - Aci Castello, Catania) where *Lethocerus* cf. *patruelis* (Stål, 1854) was found. Photo by A. Puglisi.

Fig. 3 — Occurrence of *Lethocerus* cf. *patruelis* (Stål, 1854) in Italy at regional scale, with indication of year of the first record for each region. In dark red regions with more than 50 occurrence records, in light red regions with less than 5 occurrence records.

DISCUSSION

As already discussed by CIANFERONI & MAZZA (2023), we cannot completely exclude the African closely related species *L. cordofanus*, although its occurrence doesn't seem likely. The prosternal keel matches well with that figured by NOVOSELSKY *et al.* (2018) for *L. patruelis*. However, as already mentioned (CIANFERONI & MAZZA, 2023) this feature seems too variable (unpublished data) to be considered a reliable character for separation. Therefore, as a precaution, we assigned the specific level with some doubts (as done also in some of the last contributions).

This new finding (Figs. 1-3) is very similar to the recent specimen recently discovered in Campania, in the immediate proximity of the sea (CIANFERONI & MAZZA, 2023). However, it is not possible to make deductions on a single specimen and little data. We can still stress that species of *Lethocerus* seem able to survive in sea water, at least temporarily (SCHUMACHER, 1917; CIANFERONI & NARDI, 2013) and that they are excellent fliers (DULI *et al.*, 2016), thus they can also come from very distant areas. A possible arrival of specimens from southern Calabria seems a possible scenario.

In any case, transport by boat cannot be ruled out. This is in fact one of the hypothesized pathways into Italy for these insects (see CIANFERONI & NARDI, 2013). We also reiterate that the status of this species in Italy is still uncertain since its presence can be related to a recent man-mediated (unintentional) introduction or a natural (o partially natural) westward spread. This expansion could be connected to climate change as more evident in other similar groups (see CIANFERONI & MAZZA, 2023 for some examples). Warming, presumably, could also play a key role in a possible northward shift of the species along the Italian peninsula, although since its arrival the species has not made great advances northwards.

A further obstacle to reconstructing the entire picture is that immature stages have never been detected so far (very likely due to the lack of dedicated research). Nymphs would confirm the reproduction of the species in Italy. Their possible discovery would better explain the many records for the country published so far and the colonization of other nearby regions.

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